

Research Article

Parietal Cognitive Disorders and Hyperactivity: Seriation, Dyscalculia, Dysphasia, Recursivity, and Digital Agnosia as the Core of a Common Psychopathology

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Abstract

This article describes a clinical group composed mainly of female children with signs of hyperactivity, attention deficit, and specific learning difficulties, presenting as a common core: digital agnosia, left-right confusions, dyslexia, dyscalculia, topological and spatial dysfunctions, and working memory deficits. The data were collected over four decades of clinical practice, especially in a child psychiatric hospital, and are discussed in light of classical neuropsychology. A recurrent association is observed between difficulties with dictations, complex sentences, and topological manipulations, pointing to a broad parietal dysfunction that affects the development of recursivity, self-observation, and self-regulation, forming a syndrome with a strong impact on cognition, behavior, and language.

Keywords: motor function; dynamic organization; intellectual processing

Introduction

The psychiatric cognitive examination is an essential tool in medical practice, as it enables the systematic assessment of higher mental functions, identifying deficits that are often mistaken for primary symptoms of more complex psychiatric disorders or that indicate other coexisting medical conditions. This examination helps distinguish between functional and organic symptoms [10], which, in practice, may differentiate primary or advanced symptoms of cognitive dysfunctions such as intellectual disability from the onset and/or progression of other comorbidities, including schizophrenia, mood disorders [11], and dementias (such as differentiating Alzheimer's disease, frontotemporal dementia, among others) [12]. Moreover, subtle cognitive changes may serve as predictors of poorer functional prognosis across a broad spectrum of patients and help estimate the functional impact of symptoms.

Based on the application of comprehensive psychiatric cognitive assessments in various patients within the clinical practice of an adult and child psychiatric hospital, a group of patients was identified – in this study, four cases were observed – who recurrently present: digital agnosia, left-right confusions (three are left-handed), hyperactivity, attention deficit, female sex, dyscalculia, difficulties understanding complex sentences, as well as difficulties with dictations such as: “Soft water on hard stone hits until it drills through.”

In complex sentences, impairment of working memory is observed, a typical difficulty in hyperactivity cases [1]. This impairment extends to the understanding of proverbs and grammatical manipulation of recursive structures.

Below, we list a prototypical case among these patients. We have a total serie of four such patients.

Motor Function

Kinesthetic basis of movement: Imitate with one hand the positions of the other, without visual control.

Response: One hand was covered with a sheet, and the patient also closed her eyes. The hands and fingers were moved by the examiner, but she was unable to imitate the finger movements with the contralateral hand that was hidden.

Note: Sensitivity and muscle tone preserved.

Optic-spatial organization: Hand movements in the horizontal, frontal, and sagittal planes; hand gestures forming angles (Fig. 1).

Response: Patient was able to perform the hand movements correctly but had difficulty forming angles. She seemed to have trouble understanding the tasks proposed.

Dynamic organization: Alternating and simultaneous movements of opening one hand and closing the other; tapping the right hand twice and the left once in sequence; then reversing the sequence: tapping twice with the left hand and once with the right; sequence of 3 hand positions tapping on the table (Fig. 2): pronated hand with fingers extended, pronated hand with fingers flexed, and vertical hand with fingers extended. Copy a drawing with two alternating components without lifting the pencil from the paper.

Response: Patient had difficulty performing alternating and simultaneous movements of opening one hand and closing the other. She moved slowly, sometimes opening or closing both hands simultaneously in an uncoordinated manner, with difficulty understanding commands.

Response: Patient had difficulty tapping twice with the right hand and once with the left, showing a lack of coordination; similarly for the reverse sequence.

Response: Correctly copied the drawing with two alternating components without lifting the pencil from the paper.

Figure 1: On the left, assessment of optic-spatial organization through hand gestures forming angles. On the right, hand movements performed in the horizontal, frontal, and sagittal planes to be imitated by the patient.

Figure 2: Dynamic organization: alternating and simultaneous movements with a sequence of three hand positions

Motor act regulation through speech – Draw a circle, a cross, and a square in sequence. Tap twice in response to one tap and once in response to two taps, or raise the right hand in response to one signal and the left in response to two signals.

Response: Drew out of the requested sequence, even after asking the examiner to repeat the command several times. Could not perform the tapping responses correctly as instructed.

Acoustic-Motor Organization

Response: Blindfolded, the patient was able to identify the shapes of a triangle, cross, and square. When presented with a circle, she confused it with a square; she responded quickly upon contact with the object, without having properly evaluated it, indicating possible impulsivity.

Visual Perception

Spatial orientation: Distinction between right and left. Clock hand positions: identify key features on a map. Reproduce shapes using sticks. Copy a drawing with pencil and paper.

Response: Initially able to draw the flower (fig.3 and fig.4), although with some incorrect details. Able to tell time on a clock but failed to correlate sticks 1, 2, and 3 with the image above, showing erroneous associations. Did not associate number 1; correctly associated number 2; associated number 3 with both numbers 2 and 3 (in reverse order).

Figure 3: Reference

Figure 4: Patient drawing

Figure 5: Assessment of spatial orientation using sticks

Receptive Language

Phonemic Hearing

Repeat

- Isolated phonemes (O, A, P, B, M, D, K): Correct
- Pairs of different phonemes (B-N, P-S, F-K): Correct
- Acoustically similar phonemes (B-P, D-T, G-K): Correct
- Phonemes with similar articulation (M-P, N-D, D-L-T): Correct
- Phoneme sequences (A-O-A, M-S-D, B-R-K): Reversed A-O-A, responded impulsively
- Similar phoneme sequences (B-P-B, P-B-P, D-T-D, T-T-D): Reversed P-B- P, responded impulsively

Conflicting Instruction: “Look at this gray card and this black card; if it is night now, point to the gray one, and if it is day, point to the black one.”

Response: Understood the instruction but responded incorrectly.

Inverted Grammatical Construction: “What did I do first if I had coffee after putting on my shoes?”; Is the father’s brother the same person as the brother’s father?

Response: Answered both incorrectly, impulsively, without properly reasoning.

Expressive Language

Sentence Repetition

“Today it is not raining.”

“On the same day he bought the car, he had an accident.”

“The mango tree grew in the garden behind the barbed wire fence.”

“The house caught fire, the moon shines in the sky, the rain drips on the roof.”

Response: Incorrectly repeated the last two sentences, even after being repeated twice.

Writing and Reading

Phonemic Analysis and Synthesis

Response: Incorrectly identified the second letter of the word “chave,” answering “A” impulsively.

Dictated: “P” + “E” + “D” + “R” + “A” → Incorrectly answered “PODER”

Writing-Write name and address. Dictation: letters, syllables, and words. Copying words and phrases.

Response: Initially wrote her name and address, but wrote her last name “Alves” irregularly.

Incorrect Spellings

- “favo” → “fafu”
- “pito” → “pitu”
- “chapéu” → “chapel”
- “ingrediente” → “engrediente”
- “fisiologia” → “fiziologia”
- “chave de fenda” → “chave de venda”
- “Par de meias” → “par de beias”

Wrote Incorrectly a Message to Her Daughter: “Lucia minha princesa” → “lucia minha pricesa”

Arithmetic Skills

Understanding number structure-Recognize numeric symbols. Write and read Arabic and Roman numerals. Count objects or fingers. Write large numbers. Write numbers vertically. Identify the largest and smallest in a group.

Response

- Did not interpret Roman numerals
- Correct: $13 > 6$; $96 < 103$; $1971 > 201$; $20350 > 19535$
- Incorrect: $23950 > 1320000$; $1935 > 17352$
- Under dictation, wrote correctly: 153, 72500
- Under dictation, wrote incorrectly: 17500 → “10750”
- Under dictation, wrote correctly in vertical: 790, 1530, 18900

Arithmetic operations

- $(3 + 1) =$ Correct
- $(5 \times 9) =$ Did not answer
- $(31 - 7) =$ “34”
- $(41 - 14) =$ “26”

Fill in the Missing Symbols

- $(10 - 3 = 7) \rightarrow$ Correct
- $(9 - 4 = 13) \rightarrow$ Correct
- $(10 - 2 = 5) \rightarrow$ “+”
- $(10 - 2 = 20) \rightarrow$ “+”

Memory Processing

Retention and recall

1 Minute

- Triangle hand gesture
- Phrase: “It is hot today”
- Phrase: “I woke up and came by car to ASMIGO Hospital; the traffic was heavy.”

After 1 minute, remembered only the triangle hand gesture.

2 Minutes

- Intertwined fingers gesture

- Phrase: “The table is clean”
- Phrase: “Today, upon waking, I went to the bakery and ate cheese bread.”

After 2 minutes, again only remembered the hand gesture.

Intellectual Processing

Thematic Comprehension

Describe a picture. Create a comic strip story in logical sequence (Fig. 6).

Response: Correctly described the picture but organized it in the wrong order.

Figure 6: Understanding of a comic book, in its logical sequence. The cards must be presented incorrectly.

Figure 7: Patient organization of the images.

Discursive Intellectual Activity

Problem Solving

- “Maria had 4 oranges, and Ana had 2 more than Maria; how many did they have together?”

✗ Answered: “6”

- “The farmer walked to the city in 15 minutes; another man rode a horse and arrived five times faster; how long did the rider take?”

✗ Answered: “75 minutes”

Conclusion

- Patient presents digital agnosia and asomatognosia, with difficulty understanding movements of her own body, particularly of the fingers, not reproduced in the contralateral hand, with decreased sensory feedback.
- Presents spatial agnosia, with difficulty perceiving, understanding, or orienting to spatial stimuli, reflected in dyscalculia.
- Also presents praxis motor difficulties, with problems recognizing objects through touch (stereognosis), possibly related to a frontal lobe deficit.
- Presents mild visuoconstructive dyspraxia.
- Presents deficits in working memory and sequential memory.
- Presents mild intellectual impairment

Neuro-Psycho-Pathological Conclusions

- The patient presents digital agnosia and asomatognosia, with difficulties understanding the movements of her own body, especially the fingers, which she could not reproduce on the contralateral hand, with reduced sensory feedback.

- She presents spatial gnosis, with difficulty perceiving, understanding, or orienting herself in relation to spatial stimuli, reflecting in dyscalculia.
- She also shows praxic motor difficulties, with challenges recognizing objects through touch (stereognosis), potentially corresponding to a frontal region cerebral deficit.
- She has mild visuoconstructive dyspraxia.
- She exhibits deficits in working memory and sequential memory.
- She has a mild intelligence deficit.

Further Detailing of the Findings

- We observe a group of patients – four cases – who share digital agnosia, left-right confusion (three are left-handed), hyperactivity/attention deficit, female sex, dyscalculia, difficulties with complex sentence comprehension, difficulties with proverbs (e.g., “Soft water on hard stone...”).
- In the understanding of more complex sentences, there is a working memory problem (common in hyperactivity) [1].
- These patients have problems understanding quasi-spatial sentences (Luria’s terminology), e.g.: “If João is taller than Pedro, who is shorter?”
- Right-left lateralization problems.
- Somatognosia problems: digital.
- Digital agnosia impairs math, counting, and the ordinal nature of numbers (first, second, etc.).
- Somatognosia problems impair spatiality.
- Spatiality problems impair topology.
- Topology problems impair set theory, e.g.: “Contains,” “Is contained,” “Belongs,” “Does not belong,” “Marsupials are within mammals,” etc.
- Topology also operates in notions of inclusion, union, and intersection.
- In short, topology underlies sets, and sets underlie arithmetic, as demonstrated by Cantor, Frege, and Weierstrass [3,4].
- Digital agnosia: if a person cannot count on their fingers, they cannot perform basic operations. One patient could not count using her fingers. 7 minus 3? Another didn’t know 2 times 5 was 10.
- Parietal dysfunction disconnects the patient from the external world, making them more egocentric. This may lead to hedonism or toxicomania (one patient was an alcoholic).

Parietal Problems Include

1. Spatial
 2. Somatognosic
 3. Attentional
 4. Mirror neuron
 5. Attention to objects/external world
 6. Topological difficulties
 7. Spatial difficulties
 8. Difficulties with complex grammatical structures, especially those involving recursion or paradoxes
- Problems in the frontal-parietal-attentional loop. This results in impulsivity, perseveration, praxic difficulties, and gestural dynamic issues. The patient shown in the cognitive exam exhibits several such frontal-type praxic difficulties.
 - With deficient parietal input, the frontal lobe lacks proper feedback for motor control. The frontal-parietal loop allows gestures to be inhibited or modulated. Without parietal input, the frontal lobe lacks adequate self-correction parameters.
 - Without proper spatiality, patients struggle with arithmetic layout (e.g., placing numbers one below the other in subtraction).
 - Spatiality relates to left-handedness and patients who mirror symbols (stereosymbolia), write top-down or right-to-left.
 - These patients don’t have true alexia or agraphia for numbers but struggle with
 - ordering and seriation.
 - Patients with parietal issues show:
spatial difficulties; Praxic Difficulties; working memory difficulties; somatognosic difficulties complex sentence difficulties (language); symbolism and abstraction issues; topological/set structuring issues; recursivity difficulties.
 - This leads to mixed learning disorders, behavioral disorders (impulsivity, inattention, hyperactivity), linguistic difficulties (mainly syntactic), egocentrism, hedonism, and reduced empathy (mirror neuron involvement?).

- These patients have a brain-based substrate, although classic imaging (CT, MRI) may show nothing.
- This substrate can be identified via: psychiatric-cognitive examination, clinical analysis of behavior and thought structure, developmental history (delays, reversals, hyperactivity, etc.).
- In reality, these are partial cognitive or attentional-topological developmental syndromes not described in conventional psychiatric manuals.
- They are borderline syndromes between neurology, child psychiatry, cognitive psychology, and neuropsychology, requiring a complex and comprehensive psychiatric training for proper identification.
- Patients with ordinal problems (difficulty counting in sequence, identifying middle items, etc.) also show difficulty in tasks like identifying the second letter in “cat”.
- This also links to digital agnosia: finger order corresponds to letter order. This
- disrupts seriation and sequencing capacities.
- Confusion of before/after/middle also affects complex sentence construction,
- such as:

“What Did I do First – if I Had Coffee After Putting on My Shoes?”

- Such phrases require the patient to envision themselves acting and reflecting on the action – which requires working memory.
- Parietal deficits impair this self-reflective process.
- Counting with fingers, subtracting 3 from 5, involves recursion – an act nested within an act, as seen in language and praxis.
- Fingers offer a concrete substrate for self-monitoring – the parietal cortex, mirror neurons, all serve this function of self-regulation.
- If patients lack this motor-level control, they lack it at the verbal level too.

Difficulty with Sentence: “The father’s brother and the brother’s father – are they the same?” This requires recursion, contradiction, inhibition, sequencing.

- These patients show difficulty with mirror neurons, parietal function, self-perception, recursive gesture control, impulsivity due to lack of self-regulation.
- It can all be understood as a common psychopathology.
- On the Benton test (e.g., the fan-shaped stick test), the patient performed poorly, as on the gnoso-praxic gesture-manual tasks of the Bergès test. She had difficulties with body-relative spatial tasks but did better on purely visual-spatial tests like Kohs’ cubes. This suggests issues with the mirror neuron system rather than occipital processing. Sequencing tasks revealed major deficits in motor sequencing, likely due to impaired parietal feedback to motor areas.
- There are reports that right parietal lesions affect attention processing.
- Long sentences are poorly processed because such patients must “talk to themselves” to understand, and they have difficulty receiving afferents from themselves. This resembles Wernicke’s and conduction aphasias.

Neurocognitive Findings

Spatial and Topological Difficulties

Patients exhibit difficulties understanding quasi-spatial sentences, as described by Luria [2], e.g.:

“If João is taller than Pedro, who is shorter?”

We also Observe

Right-left lateralization problems; Somatognosia, especially digital;

Digital agnosia impairing ordinal number sense (first, second, etc.); Spatial problems impair topology, which impairs set theory.

These hinder concepts such as: “contains,” “is contained,” “belongs,” “does not belong,” etc. These fundamental arithmetic notions were already addressed by Frege, Cantor, and Weierstrass [3,4].

Digital Agnosia and Recursivity

Digital agnosia implies inability to count on fingers or solve basic operations. One patient could not do 7 minus 3; another didn’t know $2 \times 5 = 10$. This reflects in spatial misalignment in written calculations, typical of functional dyscalculia [5].

Patients may mirror letters/numbers (stereosymbolia), write right-to-left or top-down.

They don’t have pure alexia/agraphia for numbers but struggle with ordering and seriation (e.g., finding the second letter in “cat”).

Recursivity and Language

These patients struggle with recursive sentences like:

“The father’s brother and the brother’s father – are they the same?”

Such structures demand recursion, inhibition, sequencing, and working memory.

E.g., “What did I do first – have coffee or put on shoes?”

This requires envisioning oneself acting and reflecting – a form of recursion [6].

Parietal and Frontal Lobe Relationship

There is a dysfunction pattern in the parietal-frontal loop:

With a deficient parietal, the frontal lobe lacks feedback to control motor acts.

Motor gestures without recursive inhibition led to impulsivity and loss of self-control.

The same pattern is found in language and executive functions [7].

Neurological Substrate and Common Psychopathology

The parietal substrate is concrete. Counting fingers is a practical recursion.

If patients lack this parietal motor structuring, they will lack it verbally and logically. Manifestations include:

- Mirror neuron dysfunctions
- Parietal deficits
- Self-awareness issues
- Self-regulation issues
- Working memory dysfunction
- Impulsivity, egocentrism

These elements form a common psychopathology blending neuropsychology, developmental psychiatry, and symbolic cognition [8,9].

Final Considerations

These patients do not suffer from a single isolated dysfunction but rather a coherent cluster of structural deficits involving topology, spatiality, recursivity, and self-control. Understanding their condition demands an integrative approach uniting child psychiatry, neuropsychology, and cognitive psychology.

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